

HYPOTHETICAL LEARNING TRAJECTORY DESIGN ON THE HISTORY OF MUSLIM SCHOLARS IN MATHEMATICS LOGIC INSTRUCTION

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Abstract

The research was aimed at developing learning resources for mathematics logic using the hypothetical learning trajectory designed through reflection on the history of muslim scholars. The subjects of this research were first semester students of Department of Mathematics Education of the Faculty of Teacher Training and Educational Sciences, Nusantara Islamic University (Uninus). In order to realize the objectives, the researchers used design research contained of three phases: preparing the experiments, design the experiments, and retrospective analysis. Preparing the experiments phase has been entired and design the experiments phase is currently under preparation. The main activities carried out in preparing the experiments phase consisted of: studies of muslim scholars, curriculum analysis, library study, and early prototype design. Design the experiments phase has enabled the development of the research instruments. The learning trajectory which has been generated in the first stage involved: reflections on the history of muslim scholars, conjunction and disjunction and their truth value in the context of muslim scholars, conjunction and disjunction and their truth value in the context of mathematics. Based on achievement of objectives and evaluation of some conjectures; strongly suspected that students' mathematical communication ability in learning mathematics logic using HLT that has been designed, increased.

Keywords: History of muslim scolars, Hypothetical Learning Trajectory, Mathematics logic, Conjunction, Disjunction

Introduction

In the process of teaching and learning, including in mathematics instruction, students who already understand a concept are expected to also communicate their understanding. Through that way, the understanding can be assessed by the teacher, and can be shared with their friends. In addition to assessment purposes, when students communicate their ideas to others, they are expected to improve their understanding. Undoubtedly, students' communication skills need to be developed.

Developing mathematical communication ability gained great attention on mathematics instruction with a new paradigm. In the practice of mathematics instruction with the old paradigm, the process of teaching and learning is defined as teaching by teachers, and learning by students. Thus, teachers are more dominant in the class, with the task of transferring knowledge to the students. Meanwhile, most students passively receive the knowledge transferred by their teacher. In mathematics instruction with a new paradigm, teachers are the managers of the learning community that occurs within the class. Teachers facilitate students, help them to understand mathematical ideas correctly, correct student's misconception; and preparing the class in such a way, so that students actively communicate during the instruction.

However, designing instruction that can facilitate the students so that they actively communicate during the instruction process, is not an easy task. Besides need for responsibility

and caring of the teachers, it is also necessary for teachers to choose the approaches, models or learning strategies that can be used as a means of achieving learning objectives, in this case develops the ability of mathematical communication. Various innovative teaching models such as Problem Based Learning, Think pair share, and Group investigation can serve as an alternative teaching model to develop students' mathematical communication ability. To achieve the intended learning objectives, teachers can also integrate history in mathematics instruction.

Based on the ideas that have been presented, the researchers are interested to integrate history of mathematics in mathematics logic instruction with the aim of developing students' mathematical communication ability. The study is titled "Hypothetical Learning Trajectory Design on the History of Muslim Scholars in Mathematics Logic Instruction". Furthermore, we formulated the following research problems: 1) How is the hypothetical learning trajectory of mathematics logic course designed using the history of muslim scholars as the learning context; 2) How is the students' mathematical communication ability on mathematics logic instruction using hypothetical learning trajectory designed using the history of muslim scholars as the context of learning.

Literature Review

Hypothetical Learning Treajectory

The term Hypothetical Learning Treajectory (HLT) first appeared in a paper published by Simon in 1995. The term is used for describe the reflexive characteristic of designing instruction and deliberating student learning in the classroom (Simon, 1995). The word "hypothetical learning trajectory" reverse its basis in a certain constructivist overview, which can be seen in the aspects of HLT. According to Simon, HLT consist of: the learning objectives, the learning activities, and the thinking and learning where in that part the students could be involved. The explanation, even though the term underline learning over teaching, Simon's characterization is designed to describe a fundamental aspect of pedagogical thinking, clearly.

In further progression, teachers and researchers developed HLT for the objective of characterizing individual student learning in appropriate content domains. This background was supported Steffe (2004), Simon & Tzur (2004), and Clements & Sarama (2004) to develop HLT for their instruction. Clements and Sarama (2004) concluded that the idea of HLT provide a unique and substantive contribution to the field. In more detail, they reveal that the design is differentiate from others in the two following reasons: involves self-reflexive constructivism, and includes the mutual consideration of mathematics instruction aspects. The intended instruction aspects are: objectives, models of student's thinking, teachers' and researchers' models of student's thinking, arrangement of instructional works, and the interaction of these at a cleared level of investigation of mechanisms. Several years after publication by Steffe, Simon & Tzur, and Clements & Sarama (2004); Gómez et al. (2007), more emphasizing HLT adaptation for the purpose of producing estimates of student learning processes.

Based on various opinions of the experts, in this study we used a simple form HLT with the following three aspects: goal, activity, and conjecture. Simply put, the HLT is presented in a table consisting of three columns: the first column contains the objectives of each learning step, the second column contains the activities or core learning steps, the third column contains the conjecture which describes the alleged response given by the student. HLT trial at the step of pilot experiment is primarily to prove the conjecture that has been formulated. Of course, the result of the step will determine the formulation of activity, and possibly the goal, of the revised HLT.

Mathematical Communication Ability

The important role of communication in mathematics instruction are expressed at least by (Georgius, 2008; NCTM, 2000; Baroody, 1993). Broadly speaking, communication can be done in two ways: orally or in writing. Oral or verbal communication is a form of communication by speaking words verbally and directly to the other person, often while facing each other. Written communication is communication done through writing as done in the activities of correspondence by post, telegram, e-mail and so on. The ability to communicate in writing is very important in mathematics, especially since mathematics is full of symbols. According to Houston (2009), the ability of mathematical communication in writing can be the ability of: writing the symbol form, using symbols according to their function, and writing or organizing a systematic solution.

In more detail, Baroody (1993) reveals that through mathematics instruction students are expected to be helpful in communicating ideas about mathematics through five aspects of communication, namely: representing, listening, reading, discussing and writing. Still according to Baroody, communication in mathematics instruction needs to be developed among the students, at least for two reasons: mathematics as language, and mathematics learning as social activity. Mathematics is a very valuable tool for communicating ideas clearly, precisely, and concisely. In other words, as a language, mathematics has other functions in addition to being a tool for: aids in thinking, finding patterns, solving problems, or drawing conclusions. Meanwhile, as a social activity mathematics instruction is a vehicle for interaction among students, as well as a communication tool between teachers and students.

Furthermore, to measure the improvement in the ability of the mathematical communication we use mathematical communication indicator as defined in NCTM standard. In the meantime, mathematical communication standards set by NCTM (2000) are: 1) organizing and consolidating mathematical thinking through communication, 2) communicating coherent and clear mathematical ideas to friends, teachers and others; 3) analyzing and evaluating mathematical ideas and other strategies, and 4) using mathematical language to express mathematical ideas appropriately.

Integration of Historical Education on Mathematics Instruction

Previously we have tried to highlight two things: mathematics as a language, and learning mathematics as a human activity. As a language, mathematics is closely related to aspects of communication. Associated with mathematics learning as a human activity, it is important to understand that mathematics is not a science that is absolutely exact and can not change. It is always growing, and has a close connection with other branches of science. According to (Furinghetti, 2002; Tzanakis and Arcavi, 2000; Tzanakis & Thomaidis, 2000), such an understanding is expected to be possessed by students through the integration of history in educational practice.

The thought of using history of mathematics in mathematics education has long been put forward. In the second half of the nineteenth century, mathematicians such as De Morgan, Poincaré, and Klein; explicitly support the integration of the history of mathematics in mathematics education. Moreover, historians such as Tannery and Loria showed an active interest in the role that the history of mathematics can enact in mathematics education. On further developments, history became a resource of diverse epistemological approaches, as well as challenging the conception of specific ideas and inferences on the learning process. Thus, over the last 40 years, the history of mathematics integration in mathematics education has been a

worldwide intensive study within the area of educational practices and research activities. (Clark, et.al. 2016).

Goktepe and Ozdemir (2013) put forward two examples of the integration of mathematical history in mathematics education, namely: 1) using worksheets about mathematicians as teaching materials, 2) activities chosen from the history of mathematics in learning certain subject. In more detail, based on survey results in several countries, Tzanakis and Arcavi (2000) describes 11 ways of applying the history of mathematics in learning mathematics. Five of which are: 1) The loading of the mathematician's story in a mathematical textbook, called the historical snippets; 2) Worksheets contain exercises or learning activities related to history. 3) Historical problems, that is using historical problems as sources of learning, for example different way to prove Pythagorean theorem in different cultures; 4) Experiential mathematical activities, that is using methods that were used in the past to solve a problem; 5) Outdoor experiences, such as visiting museums that have mathematics products in the past.

Inspired by various methods exemplified by the experts, the researchers choosed to use the history of muslim scholars (HMS) as the context of learning mathematics logic. We hope that our decision to use the HMS as a learning context can smooth the phase of mathematization that students do on learning mathematics logic.

Methods

This study applied design research method to obtain answers to the research questions and achieve the goals. Research was conducted into 3 phases: 1) preparing the experiments, 2) design the experiments, and 3) conducting retrospective analysis, (Gravemeijer & Cobb, 2006). An explanation of the three phases of the study will be presented in the description of the procedure.

Procedure

The phase of preparing the experiment contain the following two parts: preliminary design and pilot experiment. In preliminary design, this study was initiated with library study, curriculum analysis, and construct the HLT. The library study centered on: integration of the history of mathematics in mathematics education, HMS, and mathematics logic. Curriculum analysis centered on set theory and logic's syllabus and course plan. In guidance to library study and analysis of curriculum, the researchers choosed to use the HMS as the learning context of conjunction and disjunction.

In constructing the HLT, this study evolved anticipation about: method, thinking, and reasoning patterns that the students has been passed from informal to formal category. These anticipations were intended to prepare for students' reasoning strategies that appear and evolved during the learning process. The anticipation of the learning trajectory are changing and always keep renovated in correspondence with students' performance throughout the study process. Concurrently, pilot experiment phase was intended at coordinating the phase of preliminary design and design experiment. The goal of pilot experiment was to learn about students' initial abilities and their accomodation towards the learning practice using HLT constructed by lecturer. In this research, pilot experiment was hold by trying the course to eleven students at lower, middle, and upper ability class.

In the phase of design experiment, the research applied learning activities using HLT that has been developed in the phase of preparing for the experiment, particularly in the preliminary design phase. In this phase, this research compiled data about course practice in classroom and

students' reasoning process depend on the contexts of: social, mathematical practices, psychological practices; and the concept and activities of mathematics.

Concurrently, retrospective analysis was designed to analyze the compiled data from the phase of design experiment. The data involved video recorded of course practice, audio recorded of dialogue with the students and lecturers in the interview process, students' worksheet, and field-note throughout the observation. In the retrospective analysis phase, reorganizations and modification of HLT were directed beneficial to respond to the consequence of theories and the application of the HLT in more expansive context and frames.

Participants

This research engaged lecturers and first year students in the Department of Mathematics Education, Faculty of Education, Nusantara Islamic University in the academic year 2016/2017.

Results and Discussion

This study has finished the phase of preparing for the experiment and in the progress of preparing the phase of design the experiment. The major activities carried out in this phase consisted of: reflections on the HMS, curriculum analysis specifically those components associated with the syllabus of Set Theory and Logic, library study, construct the HLT; and pilot experiment. The phase of HLT construction was designed to establish learning trajectory that the students will encounter in the learning activities about conjunction and disjunction. In general, HLT that has been designed to deliver the conjunction and disjunction presented in the following table.

<i>GOAL</i>	<i>ACTIVITY</i>	<i>CONJECTURE</i>
Students can express statements in the context of the history of muslim scholars	Reflection on the history of muslim scholars	All of students can express statements in the context of the history of muslim scholars
Students understand compound statements: conjunction and disjunction	Discussion about compound statements: conjunction and disjunction	Students are actively involved in instruction, so they gain an understanding of conjunction and disjunction
Students can distinguish between inclusive disjunction and exclusive disjunction	Discussion about conjunction and disjunction and their truth in the context of the history of muslim scholars	Some students find difficulty to distinguish between inclusive disjunction and exclusive disjunction
Students are able to perform the process of mathematization: through conjunction and disjunction in the context of the history of muslim scholars to conjunction and disjunction and their truth in the context of mathematics	Mathematization: through conjunction and disjunction and their truth in the context of the history of muslim scholars to conjunction and disjunction and their truth in the context of mathematics	Students are able to perform the process of mathematization smoothly

TABLE 1 HLT in conjunction and disjunction instruction

Reflections on the History of Muslim Scholars

This activities were constructed to prepare the students with the learning contexts of mathematics logic and support them to conceive conjunction and disjunction more clearly. In the opening of the learning activities, the lecturer challenged the students to pronounce statements about the HMS. The statements pronounced by the students were starting points for establishing conjunction and disjunction statements.

Here are eight statements about the HMS expressed by the students. 1) Al-Khawarizmi is a muslim mathematician, 2) Al-Khawarizmi was born in Khawarizm Turkmenistan, around the 8th century AD, 3) Jabir Ibn Hayyan is a chemist, 4) Ibn Sina is a pioneer of medical science, 5) Al-Khwarizmi lived around the 8th-9th century AD; 6) Bacharuddin Jusuf Habibie is a scientist pride of Indonesia, 7) Abdus Salam is a Physics Nobel winner from Pakistan, 8) Al-Biruni was born in Khawarizm Turkmenistan, around the 10th century AD.

As previously predicted, all of students can express statements in the context of the HMS. According to the researchers, it is because students feel challenged by the task given by the teacher, to study the HMS. This is in accordance with the opinion of Hartono (2007) that the instructor should not focus only on the material presented in the curriculum and textbook, but must update the material with new and challenging issues, continuously.

Conjunction and Disjunction

If we are given two statements A and B , then we can constitute a more complex statement called a **compound statement** by conjugating A and B together with a logical connective or logical operator. If we use “and” logical connective to conjugate our two statements, then we get the **conjunction**, read “ A and B ”, symbolized by $A \wedge B$. If we use “or” logical connective, then we get the **disjunction**, read “ A or B ”, symbolized by $A \vee B$. There are two types of disjunction: inclusive and exclusive disjunction. The difference between the two types of disjunction will be explained in the result and discussion exposure.

This step is smoothly executed. Even though it is a repetition of high school lessons, students remain enthusiastic listening, and pay attention to teacher's explanation about conjunction and disjunction. According to the Advisory Committee on Mathematics Education (2011), one of the necessary conditions for students to learn well is to learn how to listen to mathematical explanations.

Conjunction and Its Truth Values in the Context of HMS

In this step, the lecturer asked the students to forming conjunction compound statements, by combining the statements they have declared in the reflection phase. Some of the conjunctions which are successfully formulated are: 1) Al-Khawarizmi and Al-Biruni were born in Khawarizm Turkmenistan; 2) Al-Khawarizmi is a mathematician, while Jabir Ibn Hayyan is a chemist; 3) Al-Khwarizmi lived around the 8th-9th century AD, but Al-Biruni lived around the 10th century AD; 4) Al-Khawarizmi is a mathematician, as well as an astronomer; 5) Habibie and Abdus Salam are two scientist come from Asia.

Then, the instructor asked the students to focus on the following statement “Al-Khawarizmi is a mathematician, and Jabir Ibn Hayyan is a chemist”. Next, the lecturer asked the students to analyze four possible conjunctions and identify the truth value for each conjunction as shown in the following table. The truth value of A symbolized by $\tau(A)$: T for True, F for false.

<i>A</i>	<i>B</i>	$\tau(A \wedge B)$
Al-Khawarizmi is a mathematician $\tau(A) = T$	Jabir IbnHayyan is a chemist $\tau(B) = T$	T
Al-Khawarizmi is a mathematician $\tau(A) = T$	Jabir IbnHayyan is not a chemist $\tau(B) = F$	F
Al-Khawarizmi is not a mathematician $\tau(A) = F$	Jabir IbnHayyan is a chemist $\tau(B) = T$	F
Al-Khawarizmi is a not mathematician $\tau(A) = F$	Jabir IbnHayyan is not a chemist $\tau(B) = F$	F

TABLE 2 Examples of conjunction statements in the context of the HMS

After learning the examples that has been presented, the students are estimated to effortlessly understand that the conjunction will only correct if two (all) single statements forming them, are true. Then, the lecturer asked the students to write the truth table of conjunction as follows.

<i>P</i>	<i>Q</i>	$P \wedge Q$
T	T	T
T	F	F
F	T	F
F	F	F

TABLE 3 Conjunction truth table

Almost all students record the truth table of conjunction written by one of the students on the board, in their respective notebooks. After the process of recording are finished, there is an interesting dialog in the class, the names of the students written here are pseudonyms.

- Zoya : Mam, a conjunction will only correct if two single statements forming it, are true.
- Lecturer : Exactly Zoya. Then?
- Zoya : May I say: Ibn Sina is a pioneer of medical science, and a crocodile is a reptile?
- Students : Hahahahaha (laugh)
- Lecturer : Saleem, is there something wrong with the conjunction that Zoya stated?
- Saleem : Yes, Mam! Should Ibn Sina be aligned with a crocodile?
- Zaka : I think, it doesn't matter Mam!
- Lecturer : Try to make your expression clear Zaka!
- Zaka : Ibn Sina is a pioneer of medical science is a true statement, Crocodiles are reptile is also true statement.
- Lecturer : What about the statement; Ibn Sina is a pioneer of medical science, and mosquitoes are amphibians?
- Zaka : Its Okey, Mam!
- Lecturer : Who can explain the difference between the first and second conjunctions?
- Almeera : Me! The first conjunction is true because the two singular statements are correct; the second conjunction is false, because one of the singular statements is false.
- Lecturer : Give applause to Zaka and Almeera, and thanks Zoya and Saleem for inspiring us.

Then, the lecturer told that in an exclusively logical taste, in conjunction statement $A \wedge B$; statement A and statement B do not necessarily interconnected, or adjacent meanings, or

derived from the same topic. Even supposing in mathematics and in general conversation they execute. From a logical perspective, the compound statement “Jabir Ibn Hayyan is a chemist and 7 is a prime” is an appropriate conjunction, although the two single statement come from the different topic, and there is no relation between them. The conjunction is correct since the statement of “Jabir Ibn Hayyan is a chemist” is a correct statement, and “7 is a prime” is a correct statement too. It needs to be confirmed, even though there is no connection between the single statements.

Just as predicted by the researchers, students are actively involved in instruction, so they gain an understanding of conjunction. According to observer, this condition can be achieved because of the teacher's patience and persistence in facilitating the students to understand the lessons, through designed discussions. So it should be. Through the new paradigm of instruction, the teacher must change his role, no longer as the ultimate authority holder so as to be authoritarian and indoctrinary, but to be a facilitator who helps students construct knowledge by themselves (Zamroni, 2000).

Conjunction and Its Truth Values in the Context of Mathematics

After learning the illustrations of conjunction statements in the HMS context, the students are estimated not to find obstacles to understand the conjunctions in the contexts of mathematics. The exciting debate around the truth value of a conjunction also expected to guidance the students to acquire any conjunctions whether the single statements are corresponding, have adjacent meanings, derived from the same topic; or not.

Before entering into the discussion about conjunction and it's truth values in the context of mathematics, the lecturer reminds students to notice conjunction statements that look or sound like single statement or non conjunction. For example, the statement "Al-Khawarizmi is a muslim mathematician from Turkmenistan", is a conjunction. The first single statement of the conjunction is, "Al-Khawarizmi is a muslim mathematician", while the second single statement is, "Al-Khawarizmi is from Turkmenistan". This session is passed without an intense debate that needs to be discussed here. Examples of conjunction statements in mathematics context—derived from the same or different topics, related or not, and looks like not a conjunction—are presented in the following table.

<i>SINGLE STATEMENTS</i>	<i>CONJUNCTION</i>	<i>TRUTH VALUE</i>
Derived from the same topic	$(3+8 = 11)$ and $(7 \times 3 = 21)$	T
Related	2 is an even number, as well as a prime numbers	T
Unrelated	7 is prime, and a square is a quadrilateral	T
Looks like not a conjunction	15 is an odd number divisible by 3	T
Derived from the same topic	9 is an even number, and $(21: 3 = 7)$	F
Related	25 is a square number, and $\sqrt{25} = 5$	F
Unrelated	Triangle is a polygon, and $(7-3 = 4)$	F
Looks like not a conjunction	A trapezoid is a quadrilateral that has 4 equal angles	F

TABLE4 Examples of conditional in mathematics context

In practice, all students can declare conjunctions in the context of mathematics, even if some students have to be given a stimulus in order to express the conjunction appropriately. This is in accordance with the conclusion drawn by Anghileri (2006) that an effective class for learning

mathematics is an instruction characterized by the ability of instructor to provide scaffolding so that students are actively involved in instruction.

Disjunction and Its Truth Value in the Context of the HMS

In this step, lecturer asked the students to express some disjunction statements in the context of HMS. In particular, to achieve goal so that students can differentiate between inclusive and exclusive disjunction, lecturer asked the students to focus on the following two disjunctions: “Al-Khawarizmi is mathematician or astronomer”, and “Habibie come from Indonesia or Malaysia”. There was an exciting dialogue between lecturer and students, also among the students; which are summarized as follows. Once again, the names of the students written here are pseudonyms.

- Lecturer : Hi all! Please notice the following 2 statements: “Al-Khawarizmi is a mathematician or an astronomer”, and “Habibie come from Indonesia or Malaysia”. Who can find the similarity of both?
- Zoya : Both are compound statements, disjunction statements
- Zaka : Both are true statements
- Lecturer : You were right ... Can you find the difference between the two?
- Students : Silence, ... they seemed to think seriously
- Lecturer : Notice the first disjunction, Zoya! Express the two single statements, then change the subject with Someone!
- Zoya : With a little stammerSomeone is a mathematician; Someone is an astronomer
- Lecturer : Can someone be a mathematician, as well as an astronomer?
- Zoya : Of course, Mam!
- Ramdan : Me Mam! While raising his hand. ... Someone can not comes from Indonesia, but in the same time comes from Malaysia.
- Lecturer : Great! The first compound statement is inclusive disjunction, and the second one is exclusive disjunction.
- Ramdan : Yes, now I understand
- Lecturer : Who can give another examples?
- Nitta : Me, Mam!
- Lecturer : Please Nitta!
- Nitta : Inclusive disjunction: Al-Khawarizmi or Al-Biruni are born in Khawarizm Turkmenistan.
Exclusive disjunction: Al-Haitam is optical inventor or geography expert
- Lecturer : Thanks Nitta!
I hope, in the future you guys want to study history more deeply, so you not only know Al-Khawarizmi.

Through engagement in the discussion, it is hoped that all students can understand the difference between inclusive and exclusive disjunctions. It is also hoped that students also understand that inclusive disjunction is only false if both of its single statements are false; while exclusive disjunctions are true, only if one single statement is true. Then, the lecturer asked one of the students to write the truth value table of inclusive disjunction (symbolized by \vee) and exclusive disjunction symbolized by $\underline{\vee}$) on the board as shown in the following table.

A	B	$A \vee B$
T	T	F
T	F	T
F	T	T
F	F	F

TABLE 5
The truth table of exclusive disjunction

A	B	$A \vee B$
T	T	T
T	F	T
F	T	T
F	F	F

TABLE 6
The truth table of inclusive

The conjectures formulated in the HLT are proven. Some students find difficulty to distinguish between inclusive and exclusive disjunction. However, the formulation of such conjecture guides us to be careful in instruction, continuing to provide scaffolding in such a way that the learning objectives are achieved.

Disjunction and It's Truth Value in the Context of Mathematics

This is the final step. After reviewing the various instances of disjunction on the context of the history of muslim scholars, and writing the truth table of inclusive and exclusive disjunction, the teacher facilitates the students to perform the process of mathematization. Mathematization is done by applying an understanding of the truth of disjunction on the context of the HMS, to a disjunction with the context of mathematics. Here are some examples of disjunctions put forward by students.

TYPE	DISJUNCTION	TRUTH VALUE
Inclusive	Triangle or square are polygon	T
	8 is an even number, or 15 is odd number	T
	5 is prime number, or a trapezoid is a quadrilateral	T
Exclusive	$(2 \times 5 = 10)$ or $(25 : 3 = 7)$	T
	13 is an even number, or $\sin^2\alpha + \cos^2\alpha = 1$	T
	27 is a cube number, or $\sqrt[3]{27} = 5$	T

TABLE7 Examples of conditional in mathematics context

Our last conjecture for the last step is, students are able to perform the process of mathematization smoothly. Not really smooth in fact. However, just as when studying conjunctions with the scaffolding techniques that teachers provide, students can finally understand the disjunction. *Alhamdulillah*. In all the learning steps, the need to express statements, as well as actively engage in discussion, has certainly developed the ability of mathematical communication in all students. That's an important fact we found.

Conclusions

We will present two points of conclusion, in accordance with the formulation of the problem that has been set. 1) HLT that has been designed is: Reflection on the history of muslim scholars, conjunction and disjunction, conjunction and disjunction and their truth in the context of the history of muslim scholars, conjunction and disjunction and their truth in the context of the history of mathematics. 2) Based on achievement of objectives and evaluation of some

conjectures; strongly suspected that students' mathematical communication ability in learning mathematical logic using HLT that has been designed, increased.

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References

- _____. *Principle and Standards for School Mathematics*. 2000. Reston: National Council of Teachers of Mathematics NCTM
- Advisory Committee on Mathematics Education. (2011). *Mathematical Needs: The Mathematical Needs of Learners*. Retrieved from [http://www.acme-uk.org /media / 7627/acme_theme_b_final.pdf](http://www.acme-uk.org/media/7627/acme_theme_b_final.pdf) (accessed at 26 August 2017).
- Anghileri, J. (2006). Scaffolding practices that enhance mathematics learning. *Journal of Mathematics Teacher Education*, 9, 33-52. Retrieved from [https://link.springer.com/ article/10.1007/s10857-006-9005-9](https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10857-006-9005-9) (accessed at 26 August 2017).
- Baroody. A.J. (1993). *Problem Solving, Reasoning, and Communicating*. New York: Macmillan Publishing.
- Clark, K.M. (2011). *Voices from the field: incorporating history of mathematics in teaching*. Paper presented at the Seventh Congress of the European Society for Research in Mathematics Education (7th CERME), Rzeszow – Poland, 1640-1649. Retrieved from https://www.academia.edu/2849206/VOICES_FROM_THE_FIELD_INCORPORATING_HISTORY_OF_MATHEMATICS_IN_SECONDARY_AND_POST-SECONDARY_CLASSROOMS (accessed at 25 August 2017).
- Clements, D. H., & Sarama, J. (2004). Learning trajectories in mathematics education. *Mathematical Thinking and Learning*, 6 (2), 81-89. Retrieved from [http://mathcurriculumreview.pbworks.com/w/file/attach/67386072/Clements%26Sarama%20\(2004\).pdf](http://mathcurriculumreview.pbworks.com/w/file/attach/67386072/Clements%26Sarama%20(2004).pdf) (accessed at 5 June 2015).
- Furinghetti, F. (2002). *On the role of the history of mathematics in mathematics education*. Lecture at 2nd ICTM, Crete, Greece. Retrieved from [http:// users. math.uoc. gr/ ~ ictm2 /Proceedings/panFur.pdf](http://users.math.uoc.gr/~ictm2/Proceedings/panFur.pdf) (accessed at 27 May 2017).
- Georgius, K. (2008). *Improving Communication about Mathematics through Vocabulary and Writing*. Summative Projects for MA Degree. 13. Retrieved from <http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1012&context=mathmidsummative> (accessed at 27 August 2017).
- Goktepe, S., Ozdemir, A. SW. (2013). An example of using history of mathematics in classes. *European Journal of Science and Mathematics Education* Vol. 1, No. 3, 201. 125-136. Retrieved from <http://scimath.net/articles/13/132.pdf> (accessed at 13 August 2017).

- Gómez, P, González, M.J. Lupiáñez, J.L. (2007). *Adapting The Hypothetical Learning Trajectory Notion To Secondary Preservice Teacher Training*. Retrieved from http://funes.uniandes.edu.co/424/1/Gomez_P07-2909.PDF (accessed at 13 August 2017).
- Gravemeijer, K., Cobb, P. (2006). Design Research from the Learning Design Perspective. *Educational Design Research* (pp. 17-51). London: Routledge.
- Hartono, Y. 2007. *Pendekatan Matematika Realistik*. Retrieved from http://eprints.unsri.ac.id/502/1/Yusuf_Hartono_PengembanganPembelajaranMatematika_UNIT_7.pdf (accessed at 13 August 2017).
- Houston, K. 2009. *How to Think Like a Mathematician: A Companion to Undergraduate Mathematics*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Simon, M. 1995. Reconstructing mathematics pedagogy from a constructivist perspective. *Journal for Research in Mathematics Education* 26 (2), 114-145.
- Steffe, L.P. (2004). On the Construction of Learning Trajectories of Children: The Case of Commensurate Fractions. *Mathematical Thinking and Learning*, 6 (2), 129–162. Retrieved from [http://mathcurriculumreview.pbworks.com/w/file/67909519/Steffe%20\(2004\).pdf](http://mathcurriculumreview.pbworks.com/w/file/67909519/Steffe%20(2004).pdf) (accessed at 25 August 2017).
- Simon, M. A., &Tzur, R. (2004). Explicating the role of mathematical tasks in conceptual learning: An elaboration of the hypothetical learning trajectory. *Mathematical Thinking and Learning*, 6(2), 91-104. Retrieved from [http://mathcurriculumreview.pbworks.com/w/file/67909047/Simon%20%26%20Tzur%20\(2004\).pdf](http://mathcurriculumreview.pbworks.com/w/file/67909047/Simon%20%26%20Tzur%20(2004).pdf) (accessed at 25 June 2015).
- Tzanakis, C., &Arcavi, A. (2000). Integrating history of mathematics in the classroom: An analytic survey. In J. Fauvel, & J. van Maanen (Eds.), *History in mathematics education* (pp. 201–240). The ICMI Study. Dordrecht: Kluwer Academic Publishers.
- Tzanakis, C. & Thomaidis, Y. (2000). Integrating the close historical development of mathematics and physics in mathematics education: Some methodological and epistemological remarks. *For the Learner of Mathematics*, 20(1) 44-45. Retrieved from <http://flm-journal.org/Articles/48E370DC8E2403C7C4EEF9CBBA3C9.pdf> (accessed at 12 August 2017).
- Zamroni (2000). *Paradigma Pendidikan Masa Depan*. Yogyakarta: Bigraf Publishing